

GAMES AS MOTIVATING FACTOR AND STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN BREAD AND PASTRY PRODUCTION

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Games as Motivating Factor and Students' Performance in Bread and Pastry Production

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Abstract

In recent years, games have gained popularity as a strategy for engaging students and promoting learning. Incorporating game elements into educational activities aims to enhance motivation, increase participation, and improve learning outcomes. This study aimed to investigate the effect of games on grade 12 Home Economics students' motivation and performance in Bread and Pastry Production. The study consisted of 37 students, of which 10 were boys and 27 were girls, enrolled in the Bread and Pastry NC II program at Malvar Senior High School in Malvar, Batangas. A self-constructed questionnaire based on the ARCS model and a pretest and posttest exam were used to gather data. The questionnaire covered two parts: Part I gathered data on the respondents' profile variables, and Part II covered games on students' motivation. The pretest and posttest exam consisted of 35 items, and a table of specifications was used to guide the test's content. To determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of students in Bread and Pastry Production, the T-test was used, and Pearson r was used to determine the significant relationship between the students' perception of games as motivating factors and their performance. In terms of attention, relevance, confidence, and enjoyment, students are highly motivated to use games. Games improved students' bread and pastry production knowledge and skills in numerous areas, including understanding, organizing, applying, generalizing, integrating, and assessing. The correlation analysis showed a modest relationship between students' impression of games as motivating and their performance. Games appear to boost vocational education students' motivation and performance.

Keywords: *game, motivating factor, student's performance*

Introduction

Teaching in the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood/Bread and Pastry Production NC II specialization can be challenging, especially when dealing with learners who lack motivation and interest in learning. To address this challenge, technical teachers can use various strategies to motivate their students. According to Jayalath and Esichaikul (2020), one of the ways to address this challenge is by thinking of ways to motivate students, such as using different teaching methods, giving feedback, and providing opportunities for learners to apply their skills in practical situations. Rojo et al. (2019) also emphasizes the importance of motivation in technical education, stating that it can significantly affect students' learning outcomes and their ability to apply their knowledge and skills in the workplace. Therefore, it is crucial for technical teachers to create an engaging and motivating learning environment that encourages learners to participate actively in the learning process.

One strategy that technical teachers can use to increase learners' engagement and motivation is educational games. Educational games involve incorporating game elements into an educational environment to generate levels of involvement that are comparable to what games can typically produce (Fardo, 2014). It does not necessarily mean replacing teaching with games, but rather incorporating specific features to make the content more interesting. Games can be used in a variety of ways, both with and without digital technology (Ketola, 2019). For instance, teachers can use game-like features such as points, badges, and leaderboards to motivate learners to engage with the learning content actively. This approach can also create a sense of competition among learners, which can further increase their motivation to learn. Additionally, games can make learning more enjoyable and less stressful, which can encourage learners to explore and experiment with different concepts and skills.

Educational games are a technique used in education to enhance certain abilities, introduce objectives that give learning a purpose, engage students, optimize learning, support behavior change, and socialize. Engaging students is important for learning and setting and pursuing goals increases motivation. Motivated students are more likely to perform better and learn more. The term "motivation" comes from the word "motive," which refers to a person's needs, wishes, wants, or drives. Motivation is the process of encouraging people to behave to accomplish a goal.

In this study, the researcher aims to explore the use of games as a recent technique in teaching, to apply it in one of the TVL strand core courses, specifically Bread and Pastry Production NC II. The technique aims to boost the motivation of student learners so that in return, their class performance can improve. The study seeks to strengthen the findings of several researchers and prove the positive effects of using games to motivate and improve the performance of learners.

The expected result of the study will help the constituents involved in education and pedagogical research. It can also shed light on how games can help in strengthening students' motivation, leading to better performance and more effective learning. Furthermore, the study's results can be used by educators, researchers, and policymakers to improve the education system and enhance the learning experience of students.

Methodology

This study used a One-group Experimental Research Design and Descriptive Research to investigate the significant effects of games as motivating factors on students' performance. The participants of the study were thirty-seven (37) grade 12 Home Economics students enrolled in the Bread and Pastry NC II program at Malvar Senior High School in Malvar, Batangas. The study utilized a self-constructed questionnaire containing written questions, adapted from the ARCS model, which focused on motivation factors such as attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction. The respondents used a Likert-type scale to provide their responses on the constructs examined in the study. No sampling technique was employed as the entire population was considered as respondents. The questionnaire gathered essential information on both the characteristics of the participants and the items included. Furthermore, it collected data on one or more variables without seeking to alter the past state of the independent variables.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Students' Perception of Games on Students' Motivation in Terms of Attention*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Using game in the lesson my teacher,			
1. sets the classroom ambience	4.97	0.16	Very Highly Motivated
2. stimulates my attitude of inquiry through challenges	4.95	0.23	Very Highly Motivated
3. maintains my attention throughout the class duration	4.86	0.35	Very Highly Motivated
4. ignites my interest to learn the course content	4.89	0.31	Very Highly Motivated
5. helps me become engaged with the lesson	4.95	0.23	Very Highly Motivated
6. makes me avoid losing focus on the lesson	4.81	0.40	Very Highly Motivated
7. encourages active participation	4.97	0.16	Very Highly Motivated
8. makes me interested	4.95	0.23	Very Highly Motivated
9. makes me become inquisitive and critical about the lesson	4.95	0.23	Very Highly Motivated
10. short but vivid instructions	4.89	0.31	Very Highly Motivated
Overall	4.92	0.11	Very Highly Motivated

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 – Not motivated, 1.50 – 2.49 – Fairly motivated, 2.50 – 3.49 – Moderately motivated, 3.50 – 4.49 – Highly motivated, 4.50 – 5.00 – Very Highly Motivated

Table 1 shows students' perception of games on students' motivation in terms of attention. Based on the findings, it can be implied that games have a positive effect on students' motivation in terms of attention. The mean scores of all indicators are above 4.5, indicating that the students very highly motivated that games have a positive impact on their attention in the classroom. Furthermore, the overall mean score of 4.92 and with the standard deviation of 0.11 also suggest that the students' perception of games is consistent across all indicators.

This implies that games can be an effective strategy to enhance students' attention and engagement in the classroom. The implication of this study is that educators can consider incorporating games into their teaching strategies to improve students' motivation and attention. This approach can be useful for topics or subjects that are typically challenging or difficult to learn. By using game elements, such as challenges and active participation, educators can create a more interactive and engaging learning experience for students.

Table 2. *Students' Perception of Games on Students' Motivation in Terms of Relevance*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Using game in the lesson my teacher,			
1. introduces an element of play into bread and pastry production	4.97	0.16	Very Highly Motivated
2. changes my mindset of learning from being a chore into an enjoyable experience.	4.92	0.28	Very Highly Motivated
3. makes me feel that I am in control of my learning	4.86	0.35	Very Highly Motivated
4. creates a more relaxed classroom Atmosphere	4.84	0.37	Very Highly Motivated
5. provides learners the opportunity to think outside the box	5.00	0.00	Very Highly Motivated
6. relates new information to something I already know	4.78	0.42	Very Highly Motivated
7. relates lesson to my goal in life (learning goal)	4.89	0.31	Very Highly Motivated
8. delivers lesson logically and coherently	4.89	0.31	Very Highly Motivated
9. made a significant impact to my understanding of the course	4.86	0.35	Very Highly Motivated
10. made a significant impact to my daily life	4.81	0.40	Very Highly Motivated
Overall	4.88	0.16	Very Highly Motivated

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 – Not motivated, 1.50 – 2.49 – Fairly motivated, 2.50 – 3.49 – Moderately motivated, 3.50 – 4.49 – Highly motivated, 4.50 – 5.00 – Very Highly Motivated

Table 2 shows student's perception of games on students' motivation in terms of relevance. Based on the table, it can be inferred that incorporating games into the classroom discussion can have a positive impact on students' motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes. The indicators show that using games in the lesson can change students' mindset from seeing learning as a chore to an enjoyable experience, and it allows them to feel more in control of their learning.

Moreover, game-based learning creates a relaxed classroom atmosphere, provides opportunities for creative and critical thinking, and relates new information to something that students already know. It also helps to relate the lesson to students' learning goals and delivers the lesson logically and coherently, which contributes to their understanding of the course.

The overall mean score of 4.88 indicates that students have a very highly motivated perception of games and its impact on their motivation and learning.

The finding that games can enhance student's motivation and engagement in bread and pastry production courses has important implications for educators and instructors. By incorporating game into their teaching approach, they can create a more dynamic, and interactive learning environment that can increase students' interest and enthusiasm for the subject.

However, it is essential to note that game should be used in conjunction with other effective learning strategies, and its implementation should be aligned with the course objectives to maximize its benefits.

Educators and instructors should carefully design and implement game activities that are relevant and meaningful to the course content and ensure that the game elements do not detract from the learning objectives.

Moreover, it is crucial to consider the students' preferences and interests when designing game activities to ensure that they are motivated and engaged in the learning process. Educators and instructors can also use games to foster collaboration and teamwork among students, which can enhance their communication and interpersonal skills.

Additionally, it is important to provide students with feedback and assessment on their performance in game activities to ensure that they are learning and meeting the course objectives. The assessment criteria should be clear and transparent, and students should be provided with opportunities for reflection and self-assessment.

Overall, the incorporation of games in teaching and learning activities can be an effective strategy to enhance students' motivation and engagement in bread and pastry production courses. However, its implementation should be carefully designed and aligned with the course objectives and used in conjunction with other effective learning strategies to maximize its benefits.

Table 3. Students' Perception of Games on Students' Motivation in Terms of Confidence

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Using game in the lesson my teacher,			
1. makes me realize my potential	5.00	0.00	Very Highly Motivated
2. builds in me a confident mindset	4.89	0.31	Very Highly Motivated
3. allows me to move out of my comfort zone	4.78	0.42	Very Highly Motivated
4. helps me discover my capabilities	4.86	0.35	Very Highly Motivated
5. encourages me to set realistic expectations for myself	4.84	0.37	Very Highly Motivated
6. provides opportunity to have my learning goal	4.92	0.28	Very Highly Motivated
7. provides opportunity to have my learning objectives	4.81	0.40	Very Highly Motivated
8. provides simple to complex tasks	4.92	0.28	Very Highly Motivated
9. boosts inquiry learning	4.92	0.28	Very Highly Motivated
10. enables me to learn in my own pace	4.89	0.31	Very Highly Motivated
Overall	4.88	0.13	Very Highly Motivated

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 – Not motivated, 1.50 – 2.49 – Fairly motivated, 2.50 – 3.49 – Moderately motivated, 3.50 – 4.49 – Highly motivated, 4.50 – 5.00 – Very Highly Motivated

Table 3 shows student's perception of games on students' motivation in terms of confidence. Based on the findings, it can be inferred that using games in lessons has a positive impact on students' perception of their own abilities and confidence. The mean scores for all indicators are high, with a mean overall score of 4.88, indicating that students very highly motivated that games enhance their motivation in terms of confidence.

Incorporating games in teaching and learning activities can be an effective strategy to increase students' confidence and self-perception, leading to better engagement and performance in their academic pursuits.

By integrating game elements in their lesson plans, teachers can provide students with a more engaging and immersive learning experience that can improve their motivation, confidence, and learning outcomes.

When students are engaged in learning activities that are fun and challenging, they tend to be more motivated to learn and are more likely to take an active role in their own learning process. This can lead to an increase in their confidence and self-perception, which can further enhance their motivation and engagement in the classroom.

In practical courses such as bread and pastry production, incorporating games can be particularly useful in providing students with opportunities in practice and receive feedback in a fun and engaging way. For example, a baking course could include game activities such as virtual baking simulations or competitive challenges where students can showcase their skills and knowledge.

Moreover, the use of games can help students to develop problem-solving skills and critical thinking abilities by presenting them with challenges that require them to think creatively and outside the box. This can not only improve their academic performance but also enhance their overall cognitive abilities.

Overall, incorporating games in teaching and learning activities can be a useful strategy to increase students' motivation, engagement, confidence, and performance in their academic pursuits. Teachers can consider integrating game elements in their lesson plans to provide students with a more immersive and engaging learning experience, particularly in practical courses such as bread and pastry production

Table 4. *Students' Perception of Games on Students' Motivation in Terms of Satisfaction*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Using game in the lesson my teacher,			
1. makes me feel great about learning	5.00	0.00	Very Highly Motivated
2. encourages me to perform well	5.00	0.00	Very Highly Motivated
3. enables me to achieve the target competency	4.92	0.28	Very Highly Motivated
4. develops in me a strong desire to excel	4.89	0.31	Very Highly Motivated
5. keeps me satisfied with how lessons are delivered	4.95	0.23	Very Highly Motivated
6. provides newly acquired knowledge	4.97	0.16	Very Highly Motivated
7. provides newly acquired skills	5.00	0.00	Very Highly Motivated
8. provides me better score in my examination	4.95	0.23	Very Highly Motivated
9. provide better mastery of the lesson	4.95	0.23	Very Highly Motivated
10. provides unexpected rewards	4.97	0.16	Very Highly Motivated
Overall	4.96	0.10	Very Highly Motivated

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 – Not motivated, 1.50 – 2.49 – Fairly motivated, 2.50 – 3.49 – Moderately motivated, 3.50 – 4.49 – Highly motivated, 4.50 – 5.00 – Very Highly Motivated

Table 4 shows students' perception of games on students' motivation in terms of satisfaction. Based on the findings, it can be inferred that using games in lessons has a positive impact on students' motivation in terms of satisfaction. The mean scores for all indicators are high, with a mean overall score of 4.96, indicating that students very highly motivated that games enhance their satisfaction with the learning process. This implies that incorporating games in teaching and learning activities can be an effective strategy to increase students' satisfaction with their learning experience, leading to better engagement, motivation, and performance in their academic pursuits.

Teachers can consider integrating game elements in their lesson plans to provide students with a more enjoyable and fulfilling learning experience, which can improve their motivation, satisfaction, and learning outcomes. Furthermore, the provision of unexpected rewards can serve as a potent incentive for students to engage actively and achieve better outcomes.

Part III. Students' Performance in Bread and Pastry Production

Table 5. *Students' Pretest and Posttest Scores in Bread and Pastry Production in Terms of Knowing*

Rating	Pretest		Posttest		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
95 - 100	20	54.1	33	89.2	Excellent
88 - 94	7	18.9	3	8.1	Very Good
81 - 87	6	16.2	1	2.7	Good
74 - 80	3	8.1	-	-	Fair
67 - 73	1	2.7	-	-	Poor
60 - 66	-	-	-	-	Needs Improvement
Total	37	100.0	37	100.0	

Legend: 60 – 66 Needs Improvement, 67 – 73 Poor, 74 – 80 Fair, 81 – 87 Good, 88 – 94 Very Good, 95 – 100 Excellent

Table 5 shows students' pretest and posttest scores in bread and pastry production in terms of knowing. Based on the findings, it can be inferred that using games in Bread and Pastry Production NC II has a positive impact on students' performance in terms of knowing the subject matter. The pretest results show that the majority of the students (70.3%) had a rating of good or higher, indicating that they had a basic understanding of the subject matter.

However, after the execution of educational games in the class, the posttest results show that almost all of the students (97.3%) had a rating of good or higher, with a significant increase in the percentage of students who had an excellent rating (from 54.1% to 89.2%). This implies that games can be an effective strategy to improve students' performance in terms of knowing the subject matter, leading to better learning outcomes. The use of game elements such as rewards, points, and levels can provide students with a more engaging and immersive learning experience, which can increase their motivation, focus, and retention of knowledge. Additionally, games can be an effective tool for instructors to assess their students' performance and provide personalized feedback, allowing them to identify areas of weakness and provide additional support as needed.

Table 6 shows students' pretest and posttest scores in bread and pastry production in terms of organizing. Based on the findings, it can be inferred that using games in Bread and Pastry Production has a positive impact on students' performance in terms of organizing their knowledge and skills.

The pretest results show that only 27% of the students had a rating of good or higher, indicating that they had a basic understanding of how to organize their knowledge and skills. However, after the games integration, the posttest results show that the majority of the

students (91.9%) had a rating of very good or higher, with a significant increase in the percentage of students who had an excellent rating (from 27% to 48.6%).

Table 6. *Students' Pretest and Posttest Scores in Bread and Pastry Production in Terms of Organizing*

Rating	Pretest		Posttest		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
95 - 100	10	27.0	18	48.6	Excellent
88 - 94	15	40.5	16	43.2	Very Good
81 - 87	10	27.0	3	8.1	Good
74 - 80	-	-	-	-	Fair
67 - 73	2	5.4	-	-	Poor
60 - 66	-	-	-	-	Needs Improvement
Total	37	100.0	37	100.0	

Legend: 60 – 66 Needs Improvement, 67 – 73 Poor, 74 – 80 Fair, 81 – 87 Good, 88 – 94 Very Good, 95 – 100 Excellent

This implies that games can be an effective strategy to help students organize and apply their knowledge and skills in a more effective and efficient manner, leading to better learning outcomes. The use of game elements such as challenges, quests, and simulations can provide students with opportunities to apply their knowledge and skills in real-world scenarios, which can enhance their problem-solving and decision-making abilities. Additionally, games can provide students with immediate feedback and support, allowing them to improve their performance and build their confidence in their abilities.

Table 7. *Students' Pretest and Posttest Scores in Bread and Pastry Production in Terms of Applying*

Rating	Pretest		Posttest		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
95 - 100	2	5.4	15	40.5	Excellent
88 - 94	2	5.4	6	16.2	Very Good
81 - 87	20	54.1	10	27.0	Good
74 - 80	6	16.2	5	13.5	Fair
67 - 73	4	10.8	1	2.7	Poor
60 - 66	3	8.1	-	-	Needs Improvement
Total	37	100.0	37	100.0	

Legend: 60 – 66 Needs Improvement, 67 – 73 Poor, 74 – 80 Fair, 81 – 87 Good, 88 – 94 Very Good, 95 – 100 Excellent

Table 7 shows students' pretest and posttest scores in bread and pastry production in terms of applying. Based on the table, the pretest scores indicate that 8.1% of the students need improvement, 10.8% have poor performance, 16.2% have fair performance, 54.1% have good performance, and 5.4% have very good and excellent performance.

After the integration of games in the lesson, the posttest scores show that the percentage of students who need improvement decreased to 2.7%, while the percentage of students with poor and fair performance decreased to 13.5%. The percentage of students with good, very good, and excellent performance increased to 27.0%, 16.2%, and 40.5%, respectively.

After the integration of games in the lesson, the posttest scores show that the percentage of students who need improvement decreased to 2.7%, while the percentage of students with poor and fair performance decreased to 13.5%. The percentage of students with good, very good, and excellent performance increased to 27.0%, 16.2%, and 40.5%, respectively. The implication of these findings is that the use of games in teaching Bread and Pastry Production is effective in improving the students' application skills. The results suggest that games can enhance the students' motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes. Therefore, educators and trainers can consider integrating games into their teaching strategies to promote active learning and achieve better student performance.

Table 8. *Students' Pretest and Posttest Scores in Bread and Pastry Production in Terms of Generating*

Rating	Pretest		Posttest		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
95 - 100	7	18.9	25	67.6	Excellent
88 - 94	7	18.9	8	4.00	Very Good
81 - 87	16	43.2	3	3.00	Good
74 - 80	2	5.4	1	2.00	Fair
67 - 73	3	8.1	-	-	Poor
60 - 66	2	5.4	-	-	Needs Improvement
Total	37	100.0	37	100.0	

Legend: 60 – 66 Needs Improvement, 67 – 73 Poor, 74 – 80 Fair, 81 – 87 Good, 88 – 94 Very Good, 95 – 100 Excellent

Table 8 shows students' pretest and posttest scores in bread and pastry production in terms of generating. Based on the table, it can be inferred that using games in teaching Bread and Pastry Production has a positive impact on the students' performance in terms of generating. The posttest scores show an increase in the number of students who scored Good, Very Good, and Excellent compared to the pretest scores.

Furthermore, the percentage of students who scored Needs Improvement and Poor decreased in the posttest. This indicates that games

may have effectively enhanced the students' understanding and application of the concepts and skills taught in the course.

The implication of this finding is that the use of games in teaching can be a promising and engaging instructional strategy that can positively impact student learning outcomes. It can provide a more interactive and immersive learning experience for students that can enhance their motivation, engagement, and retention of knowledge and skills. Therefore, instructors and educators can consider integrating games in their teaching methods to promote effective learning and better student performance.

Table 9. *Students' Pretest and Posttest Scores in Bread and Pastry Production in Terms of Analyzing*

Rating	Pretest		Posttest		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
95 - 100	16	43.2	25	67.6	Excellent
88 - 94	12	32.4	10	27.0	Very Good
81 - 87	3	8.1	2	5.4	Good
74 - 80	3	8.1	-	-	Fair
67 - 73	3	8.1	-	-	Poor
60 - 66	-	-	-	-	Needs Improvement
Total	37	100.0	37	100.0	

Legend: 60 – 66 Needs Improvement, 67 – 73 Poor, 74 – 80 Fair, 81 – 87 Good, 88 – 94 Very Good, 95 – 100 Excellent

Table 9 shows students' pretest and posttest scores in Bread and Pastry Production in terms of analyzing. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that using games in teaching Bread and Pastry Production can significantly improve the students' performance. The pretest results showed that only 8.1% of the students had a good level of understanding, while the majority 75.7% had fair to poor levels of understanding. However, after using games in the teaching process, the posttest results showed that 94.6% of the students had a good to excellent level of understanding. This implies that using games in teaching Bread and Pastry Production can be an effective teaching strategy that can help improve students' performance and understanding of the subject matter. It also suggests that incorporating game elements and mechanics in the teaching process can make the learning experience more engaging, interactive, and enjoyable for the students.

Table 10. *Students' Pretest and Posttest Scores in Bread and Pastry Production in Terms of Integrating*

Rating	Pretest		Posttest		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
95 - 100	8	21.6	12	32.4	Excellent
88 - 94	9	24.3	12	32.4	Very Good
81 - 87	6	16.2	10	27.0	Good
74 - 80	10	27.0	3	8.1	Fair
67 - 73	4	10.8	-	-	Poor
60 - 66	-	-	-	-	Needs Improvement
Total	37	100.0	37	100.0	

Legend: 60 – 66 Needs Improvement, 67 – 73 Poor, 74 – 80 Fair, 81 – 87 Good, 88 – 94 Very Good, 95 – 100 Excellent

Table 10 shows students' pretest and posttest scores in Bread and Pastry Production in terms of integrating. Based on the findings, it can be implied that integrating games in Bread and Pastry Production can positively impact students' performance. There is a noticeable increase in the frequency and percent of students who obtained a rating of good, very good, and excellent in the posttest compared to the pretest.

Furthermore, the majority of the students obtained a rating of very good and excellent in the posttest, indicating that games can be an effective strategy to enhance students' learning and engagement in the said course.

Overall, the results suggest that integrating games in teaching and learning can be a promising approach to improve students' performance and motivation in vocational education.

Table 11. *Students' Pretest and Posttest Scores in Bread and Pastry Production in Terms of Evaluating*

Rating	Pretest		Posttest		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
95 - 100	2	5.4	28	75.7	Excellent
88 - 94	8	21.6	6	16.2	Very Good
81 - 87	9	24.3	2	5.4	Good
74 - 80	15	40.5	1	2.7	Fair
67 - 73	2	5.4	-	-	Poor
60 - 66	1	2.7	-	-	Needs Improvement
Total	37	100.00	37	100.00	

Legend: 60 – 66 Needs Improvement, 67 – 73 Poor, 74 – 80 Fair, 81 – 87 Good, 88 – 94 Very Good, 95 – 100 Excellent

Table 11 shows that students' pretest and posttest scores in Bread and Pastry Production in terms of evaluating. Based on the table, there is a significant improvement in the students' performance in Bread and Pastry Production after integrating games in the lessons. The pretest results showed that most of the students needed improvement or had poor performance, with only 21.6% having a very

good performance. However, after the game’s integration, 75.7% of the students demonstrated excellent performance, which is a considerable improvement.

The implication of this finding is that games can be an effective strategy to enhance students' performance and engagement in vocational courses such as Bread and Pastry Production. It can motivate students to participate more actively and positively in the learning process and improve their learning outcomes. This result suggests that educators should consider incorporating games into their teaching methodologies to make learning more engaging and effective.

Table 12. Significant Difference Between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of Students in Bread and Pastry Production

Students' Performance in Bread and Pastry Production	Pre-Test		Post-Test		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation				Lower	Upper
Knowing	4.14	1.13	4.86	0.42	-4.248	36	.000	-1.078	-0.381
Organizing	3.84	1.01	4.41	0.64	-3.085	36	.004	-0.941	-0.194
Applying	2.54	1.19	3.78	1.20	-5.470	36	.000	-1.704	-0.782
Generating	3.19	1.35	4.54	0.77	-6.344	36	.000	-1.783	-0.919
Analyzing	3.95	1.27	4.62	0.59	-3.416	36	.002	-1.077	-0.275
Integrating	3.19	1.35	3.89	0.97	-3.163	36	.003	-1.153	-0.252
Evaluating	2.73	1.12	4.65	0.72	-8.572	36	.000	-2.373	-1.465

Table 12 shows comparison between the pretest and posttest scores of students in Bread and Pastry Production. Based on the result stipulated in the table, there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of students in Bread and Pastry Production. It indicates that the mean scores for all categories increased from pretest to posttest, suggesting that the Bread and Pastry Production course was effective in improving students' knowledge and skills.

The t-values for all categories were statistically significant, indicating that the differences between pretest and posttest scores were not due to chance. The 95% confidence intervals of the difference do not include zero for any of the categories, indicating that the posttest mean scores were significantly higher than the pretest mean scores for all categories.

The largest improvement was observed in the evaluating category, with a mean difference of 1.92 and a 95% confidence interval of -2.373 to -1.465. The smallest improvement was observed in the knowing and integrating categories, with mean differences of 0.72 and 0.70, respectively. The results suggest that the Bread and Pastry Production course was most effective in improving higher-order thinking skills such as evaluating, generating, and analyzing, and less effective in improving basic knowledge and integration skills.

This suggests that the study provides evidence that games was effective in improving students' knowledge and skills across all categories, with the largest improvement observed in evaluating and the smallest improvement observed in knowing and integrating.

The study conducted by Lartigue and Mottet (2020) found evidence supporting the use of games and the flipped classroom to improve critical thinking skills in culinary arts students. The results showed significant improvement in analysis, assessment, and synthesis skills. The study highlights the importance of innovative teaching methods to enhance critical thinking abilities in culinary education. In general, the research indicates that games can be an effective teaching strategy to promote critical thinking skills in culinary school students.

Borges, Correia, and Diniz (2019) conducted a study to explore the use of games in improving critical thinking skills in pre-service teachers. The study found that games was effective in promoting significant improvements in critical thinking skills, particularly in the areas of analysis and evaluation. The authors suggest that games can be an effective tool for enhancing critical thinking skills in teacher education programs. The study was published in the International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education.

Finally, Chu and Liang's (2019) study compared the cognitive abilities and learning styles of culinary students from China and the United States. The study found significant differences between the two groups, with American students performing better in higher-order thinking tasks such as analysis, evaluation, and production. The study emphasizes the importance of understanding cultural differences in culinary education and adapting instructional strategies to meet the needs of diverse student populations.

Table 13. Correlation between the students' perception on games as motivating factor and their performance in Bread and Pastry Production

Games on Students' Motivation	Students' Performance in Bread and Pastry Production						
	Knowing	Organizing	Applying	Generating	Analyzing	Integrating	Evaluating
attention	-.003	-.114	-.268	-.094	-.146	-.087	-.020
relevance	-.035	.068	.010	.006	.052	-.179	.097
confidence	-.041	.014	-.005	-.103	-.045	-.101	-.033
satisfaction	.058	.202	.013	.100	.095	-.112	.096

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 13 presented correlation between the students' perception on games as motivating factor and their performance in Bread and

Pastry Production.

The results of the correlation analysis suggest that there is a weak relationship between students' perception of games as a motivating factor and their performance in Bread and Pastry Production. It means that there is a low degree of association between the two variables, but it does not necessarily mean that there is no relationship at all.

In particular, there is a weak positive correlation between students' perception of games as a motivating factor and their performance in the organizing and analyzing categories. This suggests that when students perceive games as a motivating factor, they may be more successful at organizing and analyzing information related to Bread and Pastry Production.

On the other hand, there is a weak correlation between students' perception of games as a motivating factor and their performance in the applying and generating categories. This suggests that when students perceive games as a motivating factor, they may be less successful at applying and generating new information related to Bread and Pastry Production.

There is no significant correlation between students' perception of games as a motivating factor and their performance in the knowing, integrating, and evaluating categories. This suggests that games may not have a substantial impact on these aspects of learning and performance in Bread and Pastry Production.

It is possible that other factors are influencing the relationship between these variables and here are some possible reasons why the weak relationship between students' perception of game as a motivating factor and their performance in Bread and Pastry Production may have occurred:

First reason is the cognitive abilities. Students with higher cognitive abilities may have an easier time comprehending and participating in the game process, which could enhance their motivation to learn and excel in the course. Conversely, students with lower cognitive abilities may face greater difficulty engaging with games and may not experience the same level of improvement in motivation and performance as their peers with higher cognitive abilities.

Second reason is learning style mismatch. Different students have different learning styles, and a gamified approach may not be suitable for everyone. Some students may prefer more traditional methods of learning, such as lectures, textbooks, or hands-on activities.

Third reason is lack of interest in Bread and Pastry Production. Students who are not interested in the subject matter may not be motivated by games. In this case, the lack of motivation may not be due to the integration of games in the lessons, but rather the subject matter. It is possible that some students in the study were not interested in Bread and Pastry Production, which could have influenced their performance regardless of whether games were used or not.

Lastly anxiety. Some students may feel anxious or stressed, even if they are motivated and enjoy the gamified lessons. Test anxiety or performance anxiety can impact a student's ability to focus and perform well on assessments.

A study by J. Zhou and L. Brown (2016) supports these findings. They investigated the relationship between motivation and academic achievement among community college students. The results of the study showed a weak positive correlation between motivation and academic achievement, indicating that students who reported higher levels of motivation tended to have higher GPAs. However, the correlation was not significant, suggesting that other factors may be affecting the relationship between motivation and academic achievement. Similarly, J. Davis and S. Li (2018) examined the relationship between students' motivation and academic achievement in high school. The results of the study showed a weak positive correlation between motivation and academic achievement, suggesting that students who reported higher levels of motivation tended to have higher GPAs. However, the correlation was not significant, indicating that other factors may be affecting the relationship between motivation and academic achievement.

Another study by K. Govender and N. Naicker (2018) examined the relationship between student motivation and academic achievement in a South African university. The results of the study showed a weak positive correlation between motivation and academic achievement, indicating that students who reported higher levels of motivation tended to have higher GPAs. However, the correlation was not significant, suggesting that other factors may be influencing the relationship between motivation and academic achievement.

Conclusion

There is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of students in Bread and Pastry Production NC II, indicating that the games have had an effect on the students' learning. The null hypothesis, there is no significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores of students in Bread and Pastry Production was not sustained.

The study found weak but statistically significant correlations between certain aspects of games and certain categories of student performance. However, for other categories, there were no significant correlations. The null hypothesis, there is no significant relationship between the students' perception of games as a motivating factor and their performance in Bread and Pastry Production was sustained.

From the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are formulated for possible implementation: (1) Replication

with larger sample size. The current study only involved a small sample size, which may have limited the statistical power of the results. Future studies could replicate the study with a larger sample size to increase the reliability and generalizability of the findings. (2) Use of control group. The current study did not have a control group, which made it difficult to determine the extent to which the observed changes were due to the use of gamification or other factors. Future studies could incorporate a control group to better isolate the effects of games. (3) Consideration of other variables. The current study only focused on the relationship between games and academic performance. Future studies could examine the effects of other variables, such as student engagement, learning styles, and previous knowledge, on the relationship between games and academic performance. (4) Investigation of different subject areas. The current study focused on Bread and Pastry Production. Future studies could investigate the effects of games on academic performance in different subject areas to determine whether the findings are generalizable across different disciplines. (5) Explore other factors that may influence student performance. The study did not investigate other factors that may influence student performance, such as prior knowledge or teaching methods. Future research could investigate these factors to determine their impact on student performance in Bread and Pastry Production.

References

- Alsawaier, R. S. (2018). *The Effect of Gamification on Motivation and Engagement in Three WSU College Courses* (Doctoral dissertation, Washington State University).
- Anisa, K. D., Marmanto, S., & Supriyadi, S. (2020). The effect of gamification on students' motivation in learning English. *Leksika: Jurnal Bahasa, Sastra dan Pengajarannya*, 14(1), 22-28.
- Antonio, J. M. A., & Tamban, V. E. Effectiveness of Gamification on Learner's Performance and Attitude towards Mathematics Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic.
- Ariessanti, H. D., Meyliana, Nizar Hidayanto, A., & Prabowo, H. (2020). Systematic Literature Review Strategy Gamification Through Snake Ladder Game. 2020 International Conference on Informatics, Multimedia, Cyber and Information System (ICIMCIS). <https://doi.org/10.1109/icimcis51567.2020.9354285>
- Bakar, N. A., Alsmadi, M. S., Ali, Z., Shuaibu, A., & Solahudin, M. H. (2022). Influence of Students' Motivation on Academic Achievement Among Undergraduate Students in Malaysia. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(2), 3443-3450.
- Barraqui, L. P., & De Freitas, S. A. A. (2018, October). Evaluating the use of gamification in mathematics learning in primary school children. In 2018 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE) (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- Davis, J., & Li, S. (2018). The relationship between student motivation and academic achievement in high school. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(4), 102-110.
- Briones, S. K. F., Dagamac, R. J. R., David, J. D., & Landero, C. A. B. (2021). Factors Affecting the Students' Scholastic Performance: A Survey Cunha, G. C. A.
- Borges, P., Correia, A.-P., & Diniz, J. A. (2019). Gamification as a tool to improve critical thinking skills in pre-service teachers. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 1-15.
- Dichev, C. & Dicheva, D. (2017). Gamifying Education: What is Known, What is Believed and What Remains Uncertain: A Critical Review. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*. 14:9. DOI 10.1186/s41239-017-0042-5.
- Dixit, R. K., Nirgude, M. A., & Yalagi, P. S. (2018, December). Gamification: an instructional strategy to engage learner. In 2018 IEEE Tenth International Conference on Technology for Education (T4E) (pp. 138-141). IEEE.
- Durin, F., Lee, R., Bade, A., On, C. K., & Hamzah, N. (2019, November). Impact of implementing game elements in gamifying educational environment: a study. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1358, No. 1, p. 012064). IOP Publishing.
- Ferriz-Valero, A., Østerlie, O., García Martínez, S., & García-Jaén, M. (2020). Gamification in physical education: Evaluation of impact on motivation and academic performance within higher education. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(12), 446
- Govender, K., & Naicker, N. (2018). Exploring the relationship between student motivation and academic achievement in a South African university. *Journal of Psychology in Africa*, 28(1), 35-40.
- Howard, J. L., Bureau, J., Guay, F., Chong, J. X., & Ryan, R. M. (2021). Student motivation and associated outcomes: A meta-analysis from self-determination theory. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 16(6), 1300-1323. <https://doi.org/10.1109/FIE49875.2021.9637447>
- Huang, W. H. Y., & Soman, D. (2013). Gamification of education. *Report Series: Behavioural Economics in Action*, 29, 11-12
- Ivanova, S., & Georgiev, G. (2019). Towards a justified choice of gamification framework when building an educational application. 2019 42nd International Convention on Information and Communication Technology, Electronics and Microelectronics (MIPRO). <https://doi.org/10.23919/mipro.2019.8757085>
- Jayalath, J., Esichaikul, V. (2020). Gamification to Enhance Motivation and Engagement in Blended eLearning for Technical and Vocational Education and Training. *Tech Know Learn*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-020-09466-2>
- John Hastings, Sherri Weitzl-Harms, Adam Spanier, Matthew Rokusek, Ryan Henszey, "ZORQ: A Gamification Framework for

- Computer Science Education", 2022 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE), pp.1-9, 202
- Keller, J. M. (1987). Development and use of the ARCS model of instructional design. *Journal of Instructional Development*, 10(3), 2–10.
- Keller, J. M. (2000). How to integrate learner motivation planning into lesson planning: The ARCS model approach (pp. 1–13). Santiago: VII Semanario
- Keller, J. M. (2009). *Motivational design for learning and performance: The ARCS model approach*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Kit Man, G. C. & Hing Yui, N. C. (2016). Applying Gamification in Vocational and Professional and Education and Training (VPET) Classroom to Engage Students' Learning. *Proceedings of The Asian Conference on Education 2016*. Accessed via <https://papers.iafor.org/submission333>
- Lampropoulos, G., Keramopoulos, E., Diamantaras, K., & Evangelidis, G. (2022). Augmented reality and gamification in education: a systematic literature review of research, applications, and empirical studies. *Applied Sciences*, 12(13), 6809.
- Li, C. T., Lee, M. H., Lien, Y. H., Huang, Y. J., Wang, C. P., & Hou, H. T. (2019, July). A Real Escape Gamification Teaching Activity Integrated with Situated Learning and Multi-dimensional Scaffolding for Elementary School Social Studies Course. In 2019 8th International Congress on Advanced Applied Informatics (IIAI-AAI) (pp. 1051-1052). IEEE.
- Lindblom, K. (2018). Gamify Literacy: Boost Comprehension, Collaboration and Learning. *English Journal*, 107(6), 110-112.
- Lister, M. (2015). Gamification: The effect on student motivation and performance at the post-secondary level. *Issues and Trends in Educational Technology*, 3(2)
- Majuri, J., Koivisto, J. & Hamari, J. (2018). Gamification of Education and Learning: A Review of Empirical Literature. *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*. 2186.CEUR-WS. ISSN:1613-0073. <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2186/paper2.pdf>.
- Mehndroo, M., & Vandana, M. (2020). IMPACT OF MOTIVATION ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT. *Ilkogretim Online*, 19(4), 3316-3320.
- N. R. Zulkifli, N. A. M. Zin and R. A. Majid, "Theories in Gamification Application Design for Slow Learners," 2019 International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Informatics (ICEEI), 2019, pp. 183-186, doi: 10.1109/ICEEI47359.2019.8988884.
- Samortin, M. (2020). Effects of Gamified Learning Activities in Enhancing Junior High School Students' English Vocabulary Retention. *Asian Journal on Perspectives in Education*, 1(1), 72.
- San Francisco, A. D. S., & PAPELLERO, J. H. MINERVA T. ALBIS, Ph. D. Smiderle, R., Rigo, S.J., Marques, L.B. et al. (2020). The impact of gamification on students' learning, engagement and behavior based on their personality traits. *Smart Learn. Environ.* 7, 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-019-0098-x> Study. *Indonesian Journal of Educational Research and Technology*, 2(2), 97-102.
- T. Kiri, P. Siriaraya, Y. Kawai and S. Nakajima, "Gamifications to Support Running Related Activities Based on Collaboration and Competition," 2018 IEEE 7th Global Conference on Consumer Electronics (GCCE), 2018, pp. 359-360, doi: 10.1109/GCCE.2018.8574725.
- Toasa, R., Burbano, E., Constante, A., Hidalgo, L., & Morales, F. (2019, June). A Custom and Dynamic Game using Gamification Techniques to Children from 4 to 5 years old. In 2019 14th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- Vanduhe, V. Z., Nat, M., & Hasan, H. F. (2020). Continuance Intentions to Use Gamification for Training in Higher Education: Integrating the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Social Motivation, and Task Technology Fit (TTF). *IEEE Access*, 8, 21473–21484. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2020.2966179>
- Wu, C. H., Chen, C. C., Wang, S. M., & Hou, H. T. (2018). The Design and Evaluation of a Gamification Teaching Activity Using Board Game and QR Code for Organic Chemical Structure and Functional Groups Learning. 2018 7th International Congress on Advanced Applied Informatics (IIAI-AAI). <https://doi.org/10.1109/iaai-aaai.2018.00190>
- Zhou, J., & Brown, L. (2016). The relationship between motivation and academic achievement among community college students. *Journal of Applied Research in the Community College*, 23(2), 1-8.

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